

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THEORETICAL BASIS FOR THE STUDY OF EUROPEAN INTEGRATION

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Abstract

The assessments of the survival and development of the European Union are deprived of a seriously reliable theoretical and methodological approach. The complex system approach, which treats the European Union as an open social system, facilitates the analysis of such a complex subject and allows the formulation of research questions on the causes and mechanisms for the emergence of European Union, its equilibrium and its interaction with the environment. The proposed integrated approach includes Open Systems Theory, Functional Systems Theory, Cybernetics and Synergy. The research questions formulated through this approach allow to analyse the behaviour of the EU independently of the political conjuncture.

Keywords: European Union, integrated system approach, research questions

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Introduction

The European Union, of which Bulgaria is a member, has experienced several crises since 2008, which raise the question of its survival and further development. For Bulgaria, the results of membership in the Union are ambiguous, the question of its meaning is yet to be asked. An attempt should be made to understand in depth the logic of the EU's existence and development with a view "from the outside" and "from the inside", so as to be able to make sense of the possible scenarios for its development. Since 2010 there are numerous predictions of the break-up of the euro area, and, prospectively, of the entire Union. Such opinions are being circulated without clarity on the internal mechanisms that determine one process or another. Conspiracy theories and/or political bias contribute to the confusion. However, the lack of theoretical clarity about the nature of integration as a process, which has accompanied it from its inception, is a primary concern. 'Theories' such as 'federalism' or '(neo) functionalism' attributed to the origins of the integration community reflect rather wishful thinking and subservience to conjuncture - economic and political. At best, they represent a summary of a small body of experience, without offering a reliable method for credible predictions.

The difficulty stems from the lack of a reliable theoretical and methodological approach to such a large and complex object of study as the European Union. In the present work an attempt is made to apply the sufficiently popular systemic approach, which implies considering the European Union as an independent open system consisting of subsystems with a greater degree of autonomy, at the same time being a subsystem in the general system of international relations. European integration is seen as a process of forming an open system. Within the framework of the systemic approach or as its complement, the possibilities offered by related sciences - cybernetics, synergetics - are used.

The idea that each object of knowledge can be approached as a whole, composed of separate elements that together create a new quality other than the simple

sum of their qualities - is one of the most fruitful methodological concepts. It finds application in all fields of science, technology and social life. Systems research arose in response to science's attempts to find a general theory with universal applicability to large, complexly-organized objects such as social entities. If attempts to find a universal theory are considered unsuccessful, the application of a complex systems approach to such a complex object as the EU allows the formulation of research questions whose answers do not depend on the political conjuncture.

1. Holistic approach

The systemic approach is an extension of a philosophical movement that has its origins in classical Greek philosophy, so-called "holism". In a broad sense, this branch of science is concerned with the problem of relating the part to the whole, the qualitative uniqueness and priority of the whole in relation to its parts. (Nikiforov, A., 2010) In a narrower sense, holism is understood as a "philosophy of wholeness" developed by the South African philosopher and politician Ian Smuts, who also introduced the term itself into use (Smuts, J., 1926), building on Aristotle's claim that "*the whole is greater than the sum of its parts*" ("Metaphysics").

The statement in question is the main ontological principle of holism. On this view, the whole world is a whole, and the distinct phenomena and objects within it have meaning only as part of a community. In gnosology holism rests on the principle that knowledge of the whole must precede knowledge of its parts. (In this case, however, it is not certain that such an approach yields the best results. Without prior study of the constituent parts of the EU, it will be difficult to grasp the logic of integration: what goals each participant sets for itself through it, what price it is willing to pay for giving up sovereignty, how the goals and costs of integration change over time.)

From the holistic concept comes the systems theory with the key concept "system", as well as the often used concept "synergy" and the whole scientific field "synergetics", a derivative of the systems approach, with the leading idea of the emergence in the system of

a new quality, different from the sum of the qualities of the elements of the system.

2. Open systems theory

The term "system" appeared only in the 19th century, introduced into the natural sciences by Sadi Carnot, the creator of thermodynamics. The concept was applied to mechanical devices (steam engines), but quickly gained universal application, including in the social sciences. It became a generalization of the holistic approach. In 1850 Rudolf Clausius completed this process by adding "the medium" as a key element in the notion of the system. (Clausius' other contribution, directly related to today's attempts to apply the systems approach, is the introduction of the concept of "entropy". Clausius used it to denote the irreversible dissipation of energy and the increase of disorder in thermodynamic systems, a principle also applicable to social systems.) In the second half of the 19th c. Karl Marx, e.g., already freely used the term "system" in his study of the economized model of society. (Kuzmin, V.P., 1983) Sociology since its inception has also used "systems language".

In the 20th century there were attempts to place the concept of "system" at the basis of a general approach explaining the functioning of all observable objects. The first version of General Systems Theory to be generally recognized and accepted by researchers was that of L. von Bertalanffy, proposed in the 1930s, developing the concept of holism. Its basic idea in recognized the isomorphism of the laws governing systems - physical, biological and social. Interest in the theory remains high in the field of management, including in the study of integration problems. This theory is a logico-mathematical field of research, the task of which is the formulation and derivation of general principles applicable to "systems" in general. Bertalanffy's approach examines objects at three levels - elements, system, and metasystem, i.e., each system consists of elements, which are themselves systems, while being part of a higher order system. (By this logic, the lower limit must be set by the indivisible elementary particles, and the upper limit by the Universe in its totality.) The primary in the system is the whole, composed of elements "*in definite relations with each other and with the environment.*" (Bertalanffy L., 1968) Bertalanffy developed his theory through observation of living organisms, which he defined as "open" to the "external environment" systems: their life processes presuppose the presence of an exchange of matter and energy (information) with the environment, the exchange being governed by system characteristics. In this way, organisms acquire additional energy (and building material), which makes it possible to overcome entropy, and also ensures the resilience of the system in relation to the environment. Open systems adapt to changes in the environment and continue to function in mobile equilibrium, striving for a state independent of time and initial conditions, but only of system parameters. In dynamic equilibrium, the system structure (the elements, the relationships between them and the laws governing their interaction) remains constant, and equilibrium is constantly disturbed and restored by the exchange of matter and/or

energy. Entropy is contained by the control of this exchange. In this logic, "closed" systems can be seen as an external case in which exchange is zero. They reach static equilibrium through a limiting degree of isolation from the environment.

A viable system is one that can neutralize the unwanted inflow of information, and in the boundary (purely abstract) model of a closed system, there is simply no such inflow. "*Central to dynamic (systems) theory is the concept of stability, i.e. the response of the system to deformation.*" (Bertalanffy L., 1968) Stability, i.e., the ability of a system to maintain equilibrium by neutralizing adverse external influences, is a feature, typical for all systems.

An important research question arises in this case. With minimal exchange of matter/energy (information), control is easier. Do open systems then tend towards boundary compaction and (self-)closure? Does this logic apply to Ancient Egypt, to Rome and Medieval China in their "natural boundaries", to the USA in their isolationist period? Is the EU trying to specify its "natural" borders, e.g. in Turkey and Ukraine? Perhaps the answer lies in the dynamic of the environment. A fluid and unpredictable environment implies more of a 'closure', as the flow of matter/energy can be difficult to manage, e.g. the inflow of 'refugees'. The laws of thermodynamics are also valid here - increasing the volume reduces the relative surface area (the boundary), control over the exchange becomes easier, and the relative energy consumption decreases.

Bertalanffy tries to build a general theory applicable to all objects of study, with general laws allowing mathematical modelling. Critics have faulted him that his definition of a system as a complex of interacting elements excludes immaterial systems because of the requirement of "interaction". It limits the degree of generalization. Also, the initial conceptual and logical apparatus in L. von Bertalanffy's version is too general (Kolev, T., 1987) and key concepts are yet to be clarified: environment, interaction, etc. environment, interaction, etc.

In the case of the EU as a complex human community, the irrational quantities in human behaviour cannot be measured and put into equations. (Norbert Wiener, whom Bertalanffy himself considers a like-minded person, emphasises these limitations in attempting to apply mathematical methods to social systems.) The complexity of social systems requires a combination of qualitative and quantitative description and analysis that is in fact difficult to achieve. One of the leading systems theorists, Vadim Sadovsky, expresses the difficulties of constructing a general concept of system in a general applicable theory: "... *great doubts arise as to the possibility of constructing a single universal definition of the concept of 'system', and such that formalized sign systems, living organisms, and management systems, as well as various economic systems, science as a system, the diversity of biological systems at various levels, social systems etc.*" (Sadovskij, V., 1974)

In the case of the EU, unification can hardly be presented as a mathematical model, at least because of the obstacles in collecting reliable empirical data and

deriving the appropriate equations. Sadowski categorises the concepts that make it possible to study social systems by applying a systems approach:

- Group A, internal structure of the system: element, link, link channel, interaction, whole, subsystem, organization, structure, leading part of the system, decision-making subsystem, hierarchical structure, etc.

- Group B, system-specific properties: isolation, interaction, integration (process of creating an open social system), ..., (de)centralisation, ..., system state, system integrity, stability, perception retention and processing of information, feedback, equilibrium, rolling equilibrium, ..., (self-)management, ..., etc.

- Group B: environment, system state, behaviour, function and functioning, change, adaptation, homeostasis (equilibrium state), growth, development, equifinality, etc. (Kolev, T., 2009)

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of the system

Source: own development

(The link with Norbert Wiener's "Cybernetics" is clarified below.)

3. Functional Systems Theory

Pyotr Anokhin also developed his theory of functional systems in the 1930s as a development and continuation of Ivan Pavlov's research on higher nervous activity. Anokhin investigated the center-periphery relationship in the nervous system and his theory also aimed at universal application. The main question Anokhin poses is whether the interaction between elements, taken by itself, can create a system. After an analysis of the processes in the nervous system (the brain) the conclusion is that interaction is a necessary but insufficient condition for the formation of a system. (Kolev, T., 2009) For this purpose, factors are also needed which govern the interaction and unite the set of elements. One of the paradoxical conclusions is that the system-forming factor is precisely the end result of the system's construction. i.e., its preset desired end state. Integration (understood as the formation of a system) can be unlocked by setting some ultimate (mentally achievable) goal. The problem comes down to having a model to follow. The wish has been expressed by various political figures (including W. Churchill) to build (something like) "United States of Europe" following the obvious example of the USA. The Roman Empire, which is an essential part of (Western) European political mythology, is also cited as a relevant example.

Sadowski arranges and conducts a close examination of multiple definitions of "system" into three groups:

- Group I: definitions treating "system" as a class of mathematical models;

- Group II: definitions constructed on the basis of the concepts of "element", "relation", "relationship", "whole" with a more pronounced methodological orientation;

- Group III: definitions that include the concepts of "input", "output", "information processing", "feedback", "control", etc., which represent more specialized notions of a system and cybernetic systems in particular.

According to Anokhin, the outcome of a system's activity is a system-forming factor isomorphic to different classes of systems, and the systems approach should seek to answer the following questions:

1. What outcome should be obtained?
2. When should the result be obtained?
3. By what mechanisms should the result be obtained?
4. How is the sufficiency of the result assessed?

"We can call a system only such a complex of selectively involved components in which the interaction and interrelationship acquire the character of interaction of the components to produce a focused useful result." (Kolev, T., 2009) The outcome that results from the existence and functioning of a system can be its system-forming factor, given that every system is made up of elements that in turn can be viewed as systems, and the output system can be represented as an element within a higher-order system, a metasystem. In this sense, what results from the existence and functioning of the system within the metasystem can be seen as a necessity, necessitating the emergence of an object with certain properties. E.g. the sense organ in a living organism, being a system in itself, is built up to become part of the metasystem, acquiring the particular properties it requires.

For the first time Anokhin raises the question of the system-forming factor with a search for its "isomorphism" for different types of systems. According to his elaboration, the systems approach manifests itself in the search and formulation of the factor in question. For the purposes of the EU analysis, we seek the answer to the questions:

1. How and why does the EU emerge?
2. What does the desired end result look like that unleashes the development of the union - bringing its elements together, managing the interaction between them and turning them into a system?

Theorists of European integration work with the notion (albeit sometimes vaguely formulated) of a desired end-state, and also with the belief that in the course of integration the EU's subsystems will change, will acquire the functions required by the end-state, and new subsystems will emerge possessing these functions. These perceptions find expression in the Union's continuously complex governance scheme.

Anokhin's "Principle of the Functional System" views it as the unification of the individual mechanisms of the organism into an overall "integrative unit", by means of an adaptive behaviour to the pattern. Anokhin considers two types of functional systems:

- The first achieve equilibrium only at the expense of internal resources (of the organism), and do not seek such in the environment. These are self-sufficient and tend towards the closed systems considered by Bertalanffy - with minimal/zero interaction with the environment. In other words, the outward behavior of such systems boils down to "reaction ...to deformation" (see above) Perhaps such systems only reflect external influences? Is this logical construct confirmed by the behaviour of (self-)isolated communities - e.g. the USA and Albania in certain historical periods? The research question is: is it logical for the EU to strive for self-sufficiency (self-isolation)?

- The latter achieve equilibrium through flexible behaviour in interacting with the environment and optimising exchanges with it. Here again the question arises of the role of the external environment and its specific definition. The question is, does the EU manage its exchanges with the environment optimally?

4. Cybernetics

The theory of open systems with its refinements, as well as the theory of functional systems, have many points of contact with cybernetics, a science with roots in ancient Greece. Norbert Wiener studied the general regularities of control and information transfer processes in different systems - machines, living organisms or social entities. There is a view that systems theory is simply the mathematical equivalent of cybernetics. The main difference between the two theories lies in the emphasis they place: while Bertalanffy stresses the special importance of the exchange between system and environment, Wiener emphasizes the intra-system connections and views the functioning of the system simply as a response to external influences. The combination of the two approaches provides a good basis for the study of EU integration processes: on the one hand, it allows to examine internal development impulses, internal potential, including internal constraints,

and on the other hand, external impulses (favourable or not) and external constraints. Ignoring internal or external factors increases the risk of incorrect conclusions and explanations about the causes of integration processes, and implies inaccurate predictions about their further course.

The main task facing management is the survival of the system. Cybernetics studies the stability of material systems, their remaining in equilibrium. The striving of cybernetic systems for equilibrium is their basic internal law - in biologically appropriate behavior in animals, in conscious and socially appropriate behavior in humans, or in the EIM program. Key to cybernetics is the notion of "feedback" introduced by Anokhin: along the "sensor-control centre-executive" chain. The processing and transmission of information, as well as the reaction in response to external influences, have a direct bearing on equilibrium management. After the 2008 economic crisis, the EU is seeking to regain its internal equilibrium point, so it is particularly important to examine the mechanisms that ensure the Union's equilibrium, as well as the impulses, both external and internal, that disturb it.

Wiener gives the example of bees in a hive acting in concert, even though the nervous systems of individual bees are not directly connected to each other. "*The secret lies in the mutual communication between the members of the hive*" (Wiener, N., 1961), i.e. in the exchange of information between them. The fact that communication/information exchange is key to community building calls for an in-depth study of the specificities of this exchange within the EU. Again using the example of social insects, Wiener points out that the value of information coming from the stimulus depends not only on its nature, but also on the whole neural construction of the transmitter and receiver, i.e. the communication network. (Wiener, N., 1961) Communication requires both parties to be 'tuned to the same frequency'. The answer to the question of how the receiver understands the message depends on his senses, powers of interpretation, etc. Communication in social systems is in "symbolic language" (conditional information) and the question of the content of symbols and its uniform interpretation is raised. At the heart of the EU's 'symbolic language' are 'European values. Their content and interpretation should be studied among the different communities in the union, which may give them different meanings. The question could be asked how comprehensible the so-called 'Brussels language' is to citizens.

The distortion of information in its dissemination among a multitude can make coherent behaviour and community building impossible. In fact, the question of comparison between the individual organism and the community of organisms should not be posed in the above way - one of the principles is that the subsystem always has a higher degree of internal integrity/cohesion than the system, which in turn is more homogeneous than the metasystem. The proof is in each link of the "elementary particle - atom - molecule - cell - organism - community" chain. In the study of the EU, the extent to which the tendency to abolish the nation-state as a level of governance by devolving powers 'upwards'

(to supranational governing bodies) and 'downwards' (to districts and municipalities) is consistent with systemic logic is crucial.

Here the overlap between cybernetics and systems theory is complete and the concept of "system" is fully applicable to the study of management processes. In these, the basic outcome in the process of system formation is clearly observed. Governance is the transition of the governed system from one state to another by purposeful influence from the governing centre. (Incidentally, it can also be assumed that governance may have the purpose of keeping the governed system in the

same state by purposeful influence. This goal is possible given that the system has reached an equilibrium state.) Optimal control implies the satisfaction of some criterion - for example, expenditure of time, labor, substance, or energy. When studying a complex dynamic system such as the EU, it is possible to select such quantifiable criteria - budget, turnover, unemployment, etc., which facilitates the research task.

One of Wiener's most important insights, is the assertion that "...society extends only as far as the actual transmission of information extends." (Wiener, N., 1961) i.e., without distortion and loss of utility, without becoming "noise."

Fig. 2: Information losses when extending and narrowing communication paths
Source: own development

The question of the EU's natural borders is particularly acute in relation to the latest rounds of enlargement: how many and what other countries can be effectively governed from the centre? Is the Union still effectively governed in its present form? To what extent can the explanation for Britain's departure be sought in the inability of that country to be effectively governed by 'Brussels' as the 'quasi-imperial' centre of the union?

Here Wiener provides some methodology for determining the optimal size of a community by comparing the number of decisions coming into it from outside with the number of decisions made inside it. According to him, the measure of the effective size of a group is the size that it must possess to reach a certain degree of autonomy. (Wiener, N., 1961) Information has another feature: its value is determined not only by its quantity but also by the properties of the receiver, e.g., own information stock, ways of interaction with the environment, perceptibility, interests, etc. As Bushev emphasizes, value possesses this information "... that serves to achieve a particular purpose." (Bushev, M., 1992) If the information is irrelevant to the system's goals, it remains without consequence. Again, we return to the law that the system cannot be operated with external programs. Management information can be characterized as such a program; it is internal to the system and external to its elements.

The question comes down to measuring the number of decisions coming from outside. Is there, e.g. in

foreign trade, a limit to self-sufficiency/independence and what determines it? (Before leaving the EU, Great Britain was the only country in the union whose share in its foreign trade was under 50%.) How to ascertain the number of decisions mentioned, especially if some of them (political) remain hidden to the researcher? In this case, as Wiener himself admits, mathematical methods are insufficient and one must also work through historical review and analogies: "...whether our social science research be statistical or dynamic...it can only be accurate to a few decimal places and will ultimately never provide us with the kind of verifiable, meaningful information that would be comparable to what we have come to expect in the natural sciences." (Wiener, N., 1961)

As an example of a high degree of stability and equilibrium, Wiener cites the small rural community in which, over time, "uniform levels of understanding and behavior, ...respectable norms," and "ubiquitous public opinion" are established. (Wiener, N., 1961) The explanation obviously lies in the effective dissemination of information-formal ties are complemented by strong informal ties, each member of the small community knows everyone and communicates with them directly. Therefore, "small, cohesive communities have a high degree of homeostasis..." (Wiener, N., 1961) This explains why e.g. Switzerland is a country with a sustainable direct democracy. Relationships between community members are close and strong, information moves

quickly and without distortions along short communication paths. The small community avoids one of the main dangers to equilibrium, namely the information network (mass media) falling into the hands of "a very limited number of rich people... interested in the power and money game... which... is one of the main anti-homeostatic factors in society." (Wiener, N., 1961) (These observations apply to democratic societies where mass media are also subject to the usual market principles. In outright dictatorships the mass media are in a different mode, but this is not, or rather should not be, the case in EU countries. The presence or absence of censorship in the EU should be considered separately.)

Related to this is another important manifestation of systems thinking in cybernetics - the set may have more or less information than its members. The former case is a fundamental characteristic of human community. Obviously, its formation goes with the accumulation of a common, superior stock of information - in other words, a whole quality greater than the sum of its parts is formed. The question arises as to whether the process is reversible; whether access to the common information may be hindered and/or constricted. When the rule that common information exceeds the information of individual groups or individuals is violated, the community breaks down to lower levels of organization. According to Wiener, "...large communities subjected to (the above-described) disruptive influence have much less publicly available information than small communities..." (Wiener, N., 1961) In his view, the state is "dumber" than most of its citizens, and it is not true that the larger organization is "smarter" than the individual. (The sanity of officials in Brussels has long been questioned over some controversial directives, and this is confirmation of the validity of those doubts.)

Again comes the question of how big an effectively managed and balanced European Union can/should be. The existence of cultural "ghettos" (i.e. communities excluded from the general exchange of information) is a sign of the disintegration of a community and this is the case with the EU. However, the question arises, how can the ratio between common and private information in the EU be measured? Is the level of citizens' awareness of the Lisbon Treaty a sufficient indicator?

The question of the effective amount of public information is directly linked to the economic basis of the EU and its ideological justification. As Wiener notes, even by the mid-20th century the basis of the market economy was not sustainable ('homeostatic'). "In many countries, the view, recognized in the United States as official dogma, is widespread that free competition is itself a homeostatic process, i.e. that in a free market the selfishness of traders... will promote the common good... Unfortunately, the facts speak against this simple-minded theory." (Wiener, N., 1961)

Wiener likens the free market to the Monopoly game, subject to the general game theory developed by von Neumann and Morgenstern. Even under the assumption that each player follows a perfectly reasonable strategy based on the information available to him,

the game is complex and unpredictable, and with multiple players the outcome is most often highly uncertain and unsustainable. "Greed-driven coalitions" are temporary and typically "end in ... deceit, betrayal and fraud. This is an accurate picture of high business life and the closely related political, diplomatic and military life." (Wiener, N., 1961) It is also one of the most accurate explanations for the constant drive to establish a monopoly in all areas - indeed an attempt to reduce unpredictability and instability. Even if an agreement is reached between the players, however, "...the prize remains with the one who, choosing the opportune moment, breaks the agreement and betrays his partners." (Wiener, N., 1961) Herein lies the explanation for the periodic economic crises under capitalism and essentially a critique of the market model - from a man who has never been accused of holding left-wing (in the classical sense) views.

However, these considerations call into question the very basis of the EU's existence - after 1986 this basis is the Union's Internal Market, built on the (neo-)liberal principles of free trade and free competition. In this case, it is necessary to measure how much of Community law relates to the Internal Market. The main issues discussed in the Union's official documents always, especially after the mid-1980s, concern economic growth, financial discipline, free trade, unemployment - all manifestations or consequences of the free market. The EU's equilibrium, according to the official formulations, depends on free competition, which is a higher principle. But free competition implies a permanent distortion of equilibrium. What are the EU's mechanisms for restoring it? Can the Union's common policies be seen as 'compensatory links'?

5. Synergetics

Synergetics is the study of the relationship between structural elements (subsystems) that are formed in open systems due to an intense exchange of matter and energy with the surrounding environment under non-equilibrium conditions. In 1977, the physicist Hermann Haken used the term with the following contemporary definition of it: "A discipline that studies the joint action of multiple subsystems, resulting at the macroscopic level in structure and corresponding functioning. In such systems, there is a concerted behavior of the subsystems, resulting in an increasing degree of orderliness, i.e., decreasing entropy." (Haken, H., 1982) (In other words, the development of an open system does not follow the second law of thermodynamics - it is viable as long as it manages to maintain entropy through exchange with the environment.)

In fact, synergetics is a further development of the systems approach into a dynamic model, applying key concepts from thermodynamics and cybernetics such as entropy, disequilibrium, information, and feedback. The discipline emphasizes self-organization, the mechanism of emergence of complex systems and of transition to new, more complex systems at a higher level. It is about so-called "evolving systems". Like systems theory and cybernetics, synergetics seeks a universal law that explains processes in both living and non-living nature, in this case self-organization. By self-organization, synergetics means the spontaneous transition

from less complex and more chaotic forms of organization to more complex and more ordered ones. The principle is that processes of increasing complexity and order have a single algorithm, regardless of the nature of the systems in which they take place. These processes depend on the exchange of matter and/or energy with the environment in a state of thermodynamic equilibrium. (Here the contribution of Ilya Prigogin, who described the so-called "dissipative systems" and the way they dissipate and absorb the incoming energy from outside, is great.) Synergetics states that the evolution of non-equilibrium open systems towards increasing complexity and orderliness proceeds through two phases:

- smooth evolutionary development, until the point at which the external impact, or the accumulated internal potential (or both together) reach critical values and bring the system to an unsustainable critical state;
- an abrupt transition to a new steady state of greater complexity and order (structural change), with a qualitative change in the properties of the system, the so-called bifurcation. In bifurcation, random factors play a major role in the further development.

Applied to the EU, synergetics can answer the following questions: What triggers the self-organisation of the union - external and/or internal impulse? If it is an external impulse, does this impulse continue to operate, or has the EU become a self-contained system resistant to external influences after the initial impetus? Conversely, is the Union currently close to an unsustainable critical state, a bifurcation, and how to assess this?

The bifurcation unlocks a movement towards one of a number of possible, new steady states - so-called "attractor pools". Random factors determine exactly which qualitatively new steady state the system will move into. According to synergetics, development is in principle unpredictable - because of the role of chance, it is impossible to determine its direction unambiguously. On this line of reasoning, the future of the EU (if it is close to or already in bifurcation) should remain unclear. Obviously, using this approach alone there is no way to make a qualitative prediction about the future state of the Union. In this case, the method of historical analogies with unions that show similar systemic characteristics in similar conditions should be added. Again, it is important to take into account functional systems theory, according to which the final state is a system-forming factor. The pre-specified notion of federation is only one of many possible end states. The question is how to induce movement in the direction of the desired state if all random factors cannot be anticipated and controlled? If this is impossible in principle, then attempts at 'social engineering' (Johnson, P., 1993) are doomed and integration (if by this we mean the formation of a complex social system) cannot be a politically managed process by conscious means.

According to synergetics, randomness, irreversibility and unsustainability appear as the main source of development. In self-organization, the new order towards a more complex system emerges through the random deviations in the state and behavior of its elements. Such fluctuations in equilibrium systems are counteracted by negative feedback ('compensating linkages'),

ensuring that the structure of the system is maintained in an equilibrium state. In complex open systems, the inflow of external energy reinforces the disequilibrium, the deviations increase and accumulate. At some point, the compensating linkages cannot maintain order and the system either degrades or a new, higher order emerges. Close to the equilibrium point and with a weak inflow of external energy, the compensatory bonds bring the system to full equilibrium. The capacity for change decreases.

Again, the question arises, is this the preferred state of a system, is this not the ultimate goal of development? Every system has its life cycle: growth - culmination (equilibrium) - decline. Obviously we can refer self-organization to the first phase in the life cycle. Hence one of the main questions: which life cycle is the EU in? How far from the equilibrium point is the EU? Is the quest for trade self-containment/self-sufficiency an expression of a quest for equilibrium?

In highly non-equilibrium states, systems become sensitive to external influences. In this case, self-organization is a process in which global external impulses stimulate the emergence of new structures within the system.

A key question is whether the integration process is primarily the result of an initial external impulse. In this case, such an impulse can be found, for example, in the US's targeted policy of supporting Europe's post-war reconstruction (the Marshall Plan) and the trade closure of Eastern Europe within the framework of the Commonwealth of Independent States.

In non-equilibrium conditions, the relative independence of the elements in the system gives way to cooperation: close to the equilibrium point, an element interacts only with its neighbours; far from the equilibrium point, its behaviour is that of a 'system' element, and coherence in the behaviour of the elements increases. It is common knowledge from empirical observations of human communities that external pressure coheres, becomes an integrating factor. (Toynbee, A., 1954) It may be that by virtue of this logic the EU is now looking for such an external 'integrating' factor. Importantly, in this case, there is a way to check to what extent EU elements behave as 'systemic', e.g. by checking the economic exchange between member states: to what extent, e.g., is the movement of economic factors mainly between neighbours?

Self-organization can only take place in sufficiently complex systems, with a critical mass of interacting elements bound by so-called necessary bonds (without which the elements are non-viable). Simpler systems are not capable of spontaneous adaptation to the environment, much less development. When they receive an excessive amount of energy from outside they lose their structure and irreversibly break down. The EU is a complex system, but how complex? How much external energy can it bear? On a practical level, the question remains, e.g. how much uncontrolled immigration can destroy the structure of the Union?

Self-organization occurs only if the positive feedbacks outweigh the negative ones. In dynamically stable, adaptive systems (in a state of homeostasis), incoming external signals have the effect of permanently

returning the system to the initial state through compensatory connections. In a self-organizing, evolving system, externally induced influences accumulate and amplify due to the overall positive reactivity of the system. This leads to the emergence of a new order and new structures, as in the formation of new social formations. The question to be followed here is to what extent is the EU the result of a phase transition and is it currently entering a new one?

Conclusion

The combination of the above theories and approaches can ultimately provide the necessary theoretical basis for the study of the European Union, allowing the formulation of three groups of research questions, including those with a practical focus. The answers to these questions can explain the nature of the union, illuminate the internal mechanisms of its functioning and allow a short-term forecast of its development:

1. Questions focusing on the causes and mechanisms of the emergence of European integration:

- How and why did the EU emerge? What does the desired end result look like that triggers the development of the union and turns it into a functional system?

- What triggers the self-organisation of the union - external and/or internal impulse? If it is an external impulse, does this impulse continue to operate, or has the EU, after the initial impetus, become a self-contained system resistant to external influences? (Is it possible that the desired end result is "external"?)

2. Questions focused on the internal state of the union:

- How can one measure the ratio between common and private information in the EU and hence the degree of integration?

- How close to the equilibrium point is the EU and how strong are its compensatory links?

- To what extent is the EU the result of a phase transition?

- Which life cycle is the EU in? Is it currently close to an unsustainable critical state, a bifurcation, and how to assess this? Is it currently entering a new phase transition?

- Is the drive towards trade self-containment/self-sufficiency an expression of a search for equilibrium?

3. Questions focusing on the EU's interaction with its environment:

- Do open systems lean towards (only) closing and sealing borders, as control is easier with minimal exchange of matter/energy (information)?

- If equilibrium systems only seek to reflect external influences, is it logical for the EU to strive for self-sufficiency (self-isolation) and is there a limit to self-sufficiency/independence?

- How optimally does the EU manage its exchanges with its environment?

- How complex a system is the EU? How much external energy, including uncontrolled immigration, can it bear?

- How big can/should an effectively managed and balanced EU be?

- Is the EU trying to clarify its "natural" borders - Turkey and Ukraine?

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